

Analyzing the efficacy of LMS-based control algorithms in enhancing power quality in three-phase grid-connected systems

Abdelkader Yousfi¹, Youcef Bot¹, Fayçal Mehedi²

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology, Djilali Bounaama University, Khemis Miliana, Algeria

²Laboratoire Génie Electrique et Energies Renouvelables (LGEER), Hassiba Benbouali University of Chlef, Chlef, Algeria

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 30, 2024

Revised Aug 31, 2024

Accepted Sep 6, 2024

Keywords:

Current harmonics

Least mean square algorithm

Power quality

Reference current generation

Shunt active power filters

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel method for controlling shunt active power filters (SAPFs) to improve network efficiency and reduce carbon emissions in the utility sector. It addresses the problem of current harmonics degrading system performance by employing reference current generation based on the least mean square (LMS) algorithm, it decomposes distorted current into fundamental active, fundamental reactive and harmonic components. Traditionally, LMS implementations suffer from poor dynamic response due to uniform learning rates. To overcome this, the method adjusts the learning rates for fundamental active and reactive components separately, improving dynamic response and reducing computational complexity. Extensive analysis validates the effectiveness of this approach under various conditions, demonstrating its superiority in enhancing system performance and reducing carbon emissions in electrical networks.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Abdelkader Yousfi

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology, Djilali Bounaama University

Rue Thniet El Had Khemis Miliana, Ain Defla, Algeria

Email: a.yousfi@univ-dbkm.dz

1. INTRODUCTION

The urgency to decrease carbon emissions within the utility sector has reached an unprecedented level, necessitating a strategic overhaul in energy generation and distribution systems. A key approach in this effort is the enhanced integration of renewable energy sources into the grid infrastructure. However, alongside renewable energy adoption, optimizing the efficiency of distribution networks and loads can also significantly contribute to carbon emission reduction efforts [1], [2]. The prevalence of non-linear loads, characteristic of modern electrical systems, introduces a host of power quality issues, primarily resulting from the injection of current harmonics into the grid [3], [4].

These current harmonics disrupt the stability of the electrical system, manifesting as voltage distortions, heightened cable heating, underutilization of distribution networks, and degradation of power factor. The cumulative effect of these disturbances results in diminished network efficiency and compromises the longevity and efficiency of connected loads. Consequently, mitigating current harmonics emerges as a critical challenge in ensuring the energy efficient operation of utility networks and associated loads.

Among the arsenal of solutions to tackle power quality issues, shunt active power filters (SAPFs) stand out as effective countermeasures widely documented in literature. SAPFs not only alleviate power quality issues induced by current distortions but also contribute to reactive power compensation, thereby bolstering power factor. Central to SAPF operation is the intricate process of reference current generation, this process requires determining the phase angle of the fundamental grid voltage component and decomposing the load current into its fundamental active, fundamental reactive, and harmonic components [5], [6].

Employing least mean (LM) algorithms for signal decomposition, due to their resilience and adaptive capabilities [7], shows potential in implementing reference current generation. However, the selection of the learning rate in LMS algorithms significantly influences their performance under transient and steady-state conditions. Striking a balance between dynamic response and stability necessitates the adoption of variable learning rate strategies, as reported in existing literature. Nevertheless [8], the computational burden associated with computing individual learning rates for each frequency component remains a challenge. Moreover, alongside fundamental active component extraction, generating the reference current necessitates calculating the phase angle of the fundamental load current component [9]-[11].

This paper presents a new approach for managing shunt active power filters (SAPFs) to enhance network efficiency and lower carbon emissions in the utility sector. It addresses the problem of current harmonics degrading system performance by employing reference current generation based on the LMS algorithm, it decomposes distorted current into fundamental active, fundamental reactive, and harmonic components. Traditionally [12], [13], LMS implementations suffer from poor dynamic response due to uniform learning rates. To overcome this, the method adjusts the learning rates for fundamental active and reactive components separately, improving dynamic response and reducing computational complexity. Extensive analysis validates the effectiveness of this approach under various conditions, demonstrating its superiority in enhancing system performance and reducing carbon emissions in electrical networks [14]-[16].

2. FUNCTIONING PRINCIPLES OF SAPFS

The SAPF, situated at consumer premises, serves as a specialized power apparatus designed to alleviate harmonic currents and offset reactive power demands from the load. As illustrated in Figure 1(a), the SAPF consists of a voltage source inverter (VSI) linked to the grid via a coupling inductor L_C , positioned at the point of common coupling (PCC). Within this diagram, key variables include v_{dc} , representing the voltage across the dc -link capacitor, C_{dc} ; i_{Grid} grid, denoting the grid-supplied current; i_{SAPF} , indicating the current supplied by the SAPF; and v_{PCC} , representing the PCC voltage. The load's current, i_{Load} , comprises components such as i_{LFAC} , i_{LFR} , and i_{Lh} . i_{LFR} and i_{Lh} contribute to power quality degradation through current and voltage distortions, along with diminished power factor [17]-[19]. This detrimental effect can be averted if i_{Grid} equals i_{LFAC} , necessitating i_{SAPF} to match the combined value of i_{LFR} and i_{Lh} . Effective regulation of i_{SAPF} relies heavily on the reactive current generator.

As shown in Figure 1(b), the reactive current generator scheme comprises several components: a phase-locked loop (PLL) utilized for ωt estimation, an i_{LFAC} extractor responsible for computing i_{LFAC} , a proportional-integral (PI) controller employed to determine the reference DC current i_{dcREF} to regulate v_{dc} at v_{dcREF} , and a hysteresis current controller utilized for generating gate pulses. These gate pulses ensure that i_{Grid} matches i_{LFAC} and i_{SAPF} corresponds to the sum of i_{LFR} and i_{Lh} , thus facilitating crucial shunt compensation for harmonic current alleviation and reactive power correction [20]-[22].

Figure 1. Integrated block diagram of SAPF: (a) power circuit and (b) control system

3. GENERATION OF REFERENCE CURRENT USING THE LMS ALGORITHM

Figure 2 shows a schematic of active power filters (APFs) using the LMS control method. This algorithm's main goal is to create unit templates for each of the three phases (x_{aa} , x_{ab} , and x_{ac}) using the grid voltages that are being monitored (v_{sa} , v_{sb} , and v_{sc}), the necessary grid reference current that is being obtained by feeling the three phases' load currents (i_{La} , i_{Lb} , and i_{Lc}), the magnitude of the grid voltage (V_t), and the direct current voltage (V_{dc}) across the voltage source converter. The switching pulses for APFs are then produced by contrasting the system's measured current with the reference current that was obtained via the algorithm [23], [24].

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of an LMS-based control algorithm

At first, each of the three phases' active or in-phase voltage unit templates, namely x_{aa} , x_{ab} , and x_{ac} , can be computed utilizing the grid voltage magnitude (V_t). These unit templates, denoted as x_{pa} , x_{pb} , and x_{pc} , are synchronized with the three-phase grid voltages v_{sa} , v_{sb} , and v_{sc} , respectively, and are expressed mathematically as (1).

$$x_{pa} = \frac{v_{sa}}{V_t}, x_{pb} = \frac{v_{sb}}{V_t}, x_{pc} = \frac{v_{sc}}{V_t} \tag{1}$$

The three-phase instantaneous supply voltages (V_t) have the following magnitudes as (2).

$$V_t = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(v_{sa}^2 + v_{sb}^2 + v_{sc}^2)} \tag{2}$$

Where the three-phase voltages are instantaneously as (3).

$$\begin{cases} v_{sa}(t) = V_m \sin \omega t \\ v_{sb}(t) = V_m \sin \left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \\ v_{sc}(t) = V_m \sin \left(\omega t - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Each active weight component associated with the three phases is calculated using three distinct units. These units receive the load current as an input. By multiplying the phase template x_{pa} for phase 'a' with the appropriate weight component, a specific result is obtained. The difference between the input and output signals is defined as the error signal. Furthermore, the total output derived from multiplying the unit template by the error plus gain represents the active component of the load current for a given phase. The (4) illustrates this time-domain process for phase 'a'.

$$e_a(t) = i_{La}(t) - y_a(t) \tag{4}$$

Where output

$$y_a(t) = w_a(t) \cdot x_{pa}(t)$$

$$w_a = k \int_0^t e_a(t) \cdot x_{pa}(t) dt$$

Similarly, the active weight components for phase 'b' and phase 'c' (w_b and w_c) can also be determined. To ensure that the source current remains balanced, the average of the active weights across all three phases is denoted as w_{pA} , is calculated. The numerical representation of this value is as (5).

$$w_{pA}(t) = \frac{w_a + w_b + w_c}{3} \quad (5)$$

The direct current (DC) link voltage of the voltage source converter is detected in comparison with a reference direct current voltage to obtain an error signal. Subsequently, this error signal is inputted into a proportional plus integral (PI) controller for the DC bus voltage, yielding the direct current loss weight component (w_{cd}) [25]. The formulation for this relationship is outlined in (6) and (7).

$$w_{cd}(k+1) = w_{cd}(k) + k_p[v_{dd}(k+1) - v_{dd}(k)] + k_i \cdot v_{dd}(k+1) \quad (6)$$

Where

$$v_{dd}(k+1) = v_{dc}^*(k+1) - v_{dc}(k+1) \quad (7)$$

The parameters k_p and k_d represent the proportional and integral gains utilized in the direct current (DC) voltage controller. Meanwhile, $v_{dd}(n+1)$ denotes the discrepancy between the reference DC voltage and the measured value of the DC bus voltage. Consequently, the total active weight component can be derived by combining the average active weight component with the DC loss component, as described in (8).

$$w_{pt} = w_{pA} + w_{cd} \quad (8)$$

One way to get the reference grid currents for all three phases is to multiply the total active weight components by the appropriate unit templates for that phase. This method is shown as (9).

$$i_{sa}^* = w_{pt} \cdot x_{pb}, i_{sb}^* = w_{pt} \cdot x_{pb}, i_{sc}^* = w_{pt} \cdot x_{pc} \quad (9)$$

After that, the reference grid currents for each phase are compared with the actual grid currents. Subsequently, a 10-kHz triangular carrier wave is used as a reference signal, and each of these current discrepancies is assessed independently against it. Based on this analysis, six pulses (S1 to S6) are discovered. These pulses serve as the gate signal for the six switches of the three-arm voltage source converter.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we delve into the simulation outcomes of the envisioned active filters utilizing the MATLAB/Simulink platform. The results exhibit the resultant source voltage and current subsequent to the filtering stage, with simulation time spanning from $t=0$ sec to $t=0.5$ sec. Notably, the LMS algorithm generates a pulse following 0.04 sec, facilitating the generation of a compensated waveform for the source current. Comprehensive details regarding the parameters of the proposed system are elucidated in Table 1.

Table 1. Parametrs systeme

Parameters	Value
Single phase AC supply	100 V, 50 Hz
Line impedance	$0.1 + j0.00015$
C_{dc}	35 μ F
$v_{dc,REF}$	220 V
L_c	15 mH

The three-phase source voltage is depicted in Figure 3, and the non-linear load current for the three phases is shown in Figure 4. In Figure 5, the harmonic spectrum is displayed prior to correction. The nonlinearity of the currents is reduced to the appropriate level following the application of the SAPF, as seen in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows the SAPF current, which balances the harmonic currents from the non-linear load. Figure 8 shows a spectrum analysis following the shunt active power filter's application. The self-supported DC bus voltage is further displayed in Figure 9.

Figure 3. Three-phase source voltage

Figure 4. Supply source current without filtering stage

Figure 5. THD before filtering stage

Figure 6. Source current of three phase after compensation

Figure 7. Filter current of three phase

Figure 8. THD after filtering stage

Figure 9. DC link capacitor voltage

5. CONCLUSION

The paper elucidates an LMS-based SAPF aimed at mitigating line current harmonics originating from nonlinear loads within the system. By employing a PI controller to generate switching pulses utilizing V_{dc} reference and C_{dc} voltage for the power circuit, the effectiveness of the approach is established and validated through simulation outcomes. Consequently, the proposed system demonstrates its efficacy in curtailing harmonic content in power lines to comply with IEEE standards' permissible limits.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Emadi, A. Nasiri, and S. B. Bekiarov, *Uninterruptible Power Supplies and Active Filters*. CRC Press, 2017. doi: 10.1201/9781420037869.
- [2] R. Majumder, "Reactive power compensation in single-phase operation of microgrid," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 60, no. 4, pp. 1403–1416, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2012.2193860.
- [3] M. Gohil and A. V. Sant, "5-level cascaded inverter based D-STATCOM with LPF-BPF fundamental active current extractor," in *2017 Third International Conference on Advances in Electrical, Electronics, Information, Communication and Bio-Informatics (AEEICB)*, IEEE, Feb. 2017, pp. 237–241. doi: 10.1109/AEEICB.2017.7972420.
- [4] R. Martinek, J. Manas, J. Zidek, and P. Bilik, "Power quality improvement by shunt active performance filters emulated by artificial intelligence techniques," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computer Science and Engineering*, Paris, France: Atlantis Press, 2013. doi: 10.2991/cse.2013.37.
- [5] F. Z. Peng, "Application issues of active power filters," *IEEE Industry Applications Magazine*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 21–30, 1998, doi: 10.1109/2943.715502.
- [6] S. T. Meraj *et al.*, "A filter less improved control scheme for active/reactive energy management in fuel cell integrated grid system with harmonic reduction ability," *Applied Energy*, vol. 312, p. 118784, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.118784.
- [7] R. Martinek, J. Rzigly, R. Jaros, P. Bilik, and M. Ladrova, "Least mean squares and recursive least squares algorithms for total harmonic distortion reduction using shunt active power filter control," *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 8, p. 1545, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12081545.
- [8] S. Haykin and B. Widrow, *Least-mean-square adaptive filters*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2003. doi: 10.1002/0471461288.
- [9] M. Srinivas, I. Hussain, and B. Singh, "Combined LMS–LMF-based control algorithm of DSTATCOM for power quality enhancement in distribution system," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 7, pp. 4160–4168, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2016.2532278.
- [10] K. C. Patel, A. V. Sant, and M. H. Gohil, "Shunt active filtering with NARX feedback neural networks based reference current generation," in *2017 International Conference on Power and Embedded Drive Control (ICPEDC)*, IEEE, Mar. 2017, pp. 280–285. doi: 10.1109/ICPEDC.2017.8081101.
- [11] M. C. Benhabib and S. Saadate, "A new topology for a modular active power filter," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics, 2005. ISIE 2005.*, IEEE, 2005, pp. 827–832 vol. 2. doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2005.1529022.
- [12] D. Chen, L. Xiao, W. Yan, Y. Li, and Y. Guo, "A harmonics detection method based on triangle orthogonal principle for shunt active power filter," *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 98–104, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.06.016.
- [13] M. Ahmad and S. Kirmani, "Performance analysis of LMS based control algorithm for power quality improvement in three phase grid connected system for linear/non-linear load," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 1944, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.pp1944-1950.
- [14] R. K. Agarwal, I. Hussain, and B. Singh, "LMF-based control algorithm for single stage three-phase grid integrated solar PV System," *IEEE Trans Sustain Energy*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1379–1387, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2016.2553181.
- [15] T. Khan, M. Asim, M. S. Manzar, M. Ibrahim, and S. S. A. Ahmed, "Least mean sixth control approach for three-phase three-wire grid-integrated PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 2131, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2131-2139.

- [16] S. Khalid, "Application of adaptive tabu search algorithm in hybrid power filter and shunt active power filters: Application of ATS algorithm in HPF and APF," in *Sustaining Power Resources through Energy Optimization and Engineering*, 2016, pp. 276–307. doi: 10.4018/978-1-4666-9755-3.ch012.
- [17] S. Khalid, "A novel algorithm adaptive autarchoglossans lizard foraging (AALF) in a shunt active power filter connected to MPPT-based photovoltaic array," *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, vol. 3, p. 100100, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.prime.2022.100100.
- [18] S. K. Patel, S. R. Arya, and R. Maurya, "Optimal step LMS-based control algorithm for DSTATCOM in distribution system," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 47, no. 8, pp. 675–691, May 2019, doi: 10.1080/15325008.2019.1602797.
- [19] S. Khalid, "Performance evaluation of GA optimized shunt active power filter for constant frequency aircraft power system," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Informatics (IJEI)*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 112–119, 2016.
- [20] A. Yousfi, T. Allaoui, and A. Chaker, "Harmonic current compensation and reactive power based on three-level shunt active filter controlled by fuzzy logic connected to a photovoltaic source," *International Review of Automatic Control (IREACO)*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 56, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.15866/ireaco.v8i1.5074.
- [21] A. Yousfi, T. Allaoui, and A. Chaker, "A new approach to extract reference currents for multilevel shunt active filter in three phase systems," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 1459, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.pp1459-1467.
- [22] A. Yousfi, Y. Bot, F. Mehedi, and A. Chaker, "Current model predictive control for three-phase active power filter using cascaded H-bridge multilevel converter," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 714–722, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v21.i2.pp714-722.
- [23] S. R. Arya and B. Singh, "Performance of DSTATCOM using leaky LMS control algorithm," *IEEE J Emerg Sel Top Power Electron*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 104–113, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2013.2266372.
- [24] R. Rajagopal, K. Palanisamy, and S. Paramasivam, "Comparative performance of normalized LMS and variable step size LMS based control for shunt active filtering," in *2019 9th International Conference on Advances in Computing and Communication (ICACC)*, IEEE, Nov. 2019, pp. 136–141. doi: 10.1109/ICACC48162.2019.8986184.
- [25] R. N. Rao, M. Sreenivasulu, and B. Ramakrishna, "Study and analysis of modified LMF control method for power quality improvement," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 14, no. 2, p. 992, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i2.pp992-1000.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Abdelkader Yousfi was born on December 18, 1982, in Ain Defla, Algeria. He currently works as a professor at Khemis Miliana University in Algeria. In 2005, he earned an engineering degree in Electrotechnics, and in 2008, he obtained a master's degree in Electrotechnics from the University of Chlef in Algeria. He received a Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering from the National Polytechnic School of Oran, Algeria, in 2017. He is a researcher in power electronics, artificial intelligence, active power filter, renewable energy, studying FACTS and their impact on the electrical grid, and studying future power networks. He can be contacted at email: yousfi_pg@yahoo.fr.

Youcef Bot was born on 8 November 1979 in Munich in Germany. He is currently a senior lecturer at the University of Khemis Miliana, Algeria. In 2004, he graduated at the Electrotechnics Department at Tiaret University in Algeria. He received the magister and the Ph.D. degrees from the University of Sciences and Technology of Oran, Algeria in 2011 and 2016 respectively all in Electrical Engineering. His scientific research is focusing on load flow and real time simulation of power systems, and the study of FACTS and their influence on the electricity network and study of the future networks electrical supply. He can be contacted at email: bot_youcef@yahoo.fr.

Fayçal Mehedi received his engineer and M.S. degrees in Electrical Engineering from the Hassiba Benbouali University of Chlef, Algeria, in 2007 and 2011, respectively. He received the Ph.D. in Automatic from Ecole Nationale Polytechnique (ENP), Algiers, Algeria in 2019. He is currently an associate professor at the Hassiba Benbouali University of Chlef. His research interest includes power electronics, artificial intelligence, observers, multi-machine system, application of robust and nonlinear control in electrical machines and wind turbine systems. He can be contacted at email: faycalmehedi@yahoo.fr.